

Deliverable 5.2

Secondary use of vaccine trial data

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Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable	ECRIN, UiO		
Authors	Gerd Felder (ECRIN), Sergio Contrino (ECRIN), Christian Ohmann (ECRIN), Léopold Cudilla (ECRIN), Maria Panagiotopoulou (ECRIN), Mihaela Matei (ECRIN), Milen Kouylekov (UiO), Russel Gene Wolff (UiO)		
Contributors	N/A		
Acknowledgements (not grant participants)	N/A		
Reviewers	Robin Navest (Lygature), Nina Van Goethem (Sciensano), Ilaria Colussi (BBMRI-ERIC), Louiza Kalokairinou (ELIXIR)		

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Date	Mvm	Who	Description
06/09/2024		Gerd Felder (ECRIN), Sergio Contrino (ECRIN), Christian Ohmann (ECRIN), Léopold Cudilla (ECRIN), Maria Panagiotopoulou (ECRIN), Mihaela Matei (ECRIN), Milen Kouylekov (UiO), Russel Gene Wolff (UiO)	Version 1 of D5.2 sent for BY-COVID internal review
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1. Executive Summary

The scope of *D5.2 Secondary use of vaccine trial data* is to describe the actions taken within the BY-COVID project to improve clinical trial data sharing and secondary use in a pandemic context, utilising COVID-19 trials as a use case. Secondary use of clinical trial data allows independent researchers to validate findings, test new hypotheses without additional patient interventions, and improve trial designs and methods. It supports regulatory safety studies, facilitates research collaborations like meta-analyses, and helps develop new healthcare technologies, such as AI-based algorithms. Since the adoption of the FAIR principles in 2016, key organisations have promoted data sharing to enhance research transparency, validity, and maximise the return on research investment.

Despite this “call for action” from major stakeholders, clinical trial data sharing remains low. Indeed, implementing data sharing in a clinical trial requires several steps at different stages of the clinical trial lifecycle (*pre-trial*, during *trial set-up*, at *the end of the trial*, at the *data sharing stage*). The European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN) and the University of Oslo (UiO) developed the clinical research Data Sharing Repository (crDSR, <https://crdsr.ecriin.org/>) to provide a secure, ethically, and legally compliant platform for sharing clinical research data based in the EU.

The crDSR is currently being piloted for the data sharing of the VACCELERATE-funded trial EU-COVAT-1 AGED. EU-COVAT-1 AGED is a multinational, phase 2 trial assessing the immunogenicity and reactogenicity of different COVID-19 vaccines in older adults. Despite several data sharing steps being already implemented (*e.g., inclusion of data sharing section in the clinical trial protocol, developing a dedicated Patient Information Sheet and Informed Consent Form for secondary use, utilisation of interoperability standards developed by the Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC, <https://www.cdisc.org/>), initiation of the Data Transfer Process within the crDSR, negotiation of a Data Transfer Agreement with the crDSR*) the trial faced significant delays that have pushed the timeline for completion of all data sharing steps to December 2024. The delays were mainly due to the evolving public health policies across Europe, such as for example the recommendation for a third vaccination dose to higher risk groups or the orientation towards variant-specific vaccines that impacted the trial conduct (several amendments of the trial protocol necessary) and recruitment.

In search of alternative use cases, COVID-19 studies were identified for potential data sharing via the crDSR, using the ECRIN MetaData Repository (crMDR, <https://crmdr.ecriin.org/>). Out of 7,618 COVID-19 registered studies, 1,261 (16.55%) indicated willingness to share data. The BY-COVID team developed a classification system to evaluate the Data Sharing Statements (DSS) and applied it to a sample of 200 studies providing a BY-COVID inventory of selected studies categorised by the likelihood to share data. From this inventory 131 studies that were categorised as highly likely to share data but had not employed a designated repository were contacted with a follow-up survey to

clarify their data sharing conditions and eventually provide additional piloting exercises for crDSR. Around 75% of the respondents remained open to data sharing, with 25% answering “Yes” to an eventual collaboration with the crDSR for making their Individual Participant Data (IPD) available for secondary use.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Enable storage, sharing, access, analysis and processing of research data and other digital research objects from outbreak research	1. A research data management practice in European research infrastructures that drives discovery, access and reuse of outbreak data and directly links experimental data from HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EMERGENCY-02 transnational access projects into the COVID-19 Data Portal .	No
	2. Workflows and processing pipelines that integrate transparent quality management and provenance and are openly shared.	No
	3. Research infrastructures on-target training so that users can exploit the platform.	No
	4. Engagement so that stakeholders (RI, national centres, policy makers, intergovernmental organisations, funders and end-users) incorporate FAIR and open data in infectious disease guidelines and forward planning.	Yes
Objective 2 Mobilise and expose viral and human infectious disease data from national centres	1. A comprehensive registry of available data with established procedures to collate data governance models, metadata descriptions and access mechanisms in a pandemic scenario.	No
	2. Mechanisms for the initial discovery across data sources based on available metadata at the reference collection.	No
	3. Demonstrated transnational linking of real-world data from national surveillance, healthcare, registries and social science data that allow the assessment of variants to serve the research needs of epidemiology and public health.	No
	4. Demonstrated assessment of emerging SARS-CoV-2 variants against data generated in the on-going European	Yes

	VACCELERATE clinical trials project to investigate vaccine efficacy.	
Objective 3 Link FAIR data and metadata on SARS-CoV-2 and COVID-19	1. A platform that links normative pathogen genomes and variant representations to research cohorts and mechanistic studies to understand the biomolecular determinants of variant response on patient susceptibility, and disease pathways.	No
	2. An open and extensible metadata framework adopted cross-domain that supports comprehensive indexing of the infectious disease resources based on mappings across resources and research domains.	No
	3. A provenance framework for researchers and policy-makers that enables trust in results and credit to data submitters, workflow contributors and participant resources.	No
Objective 4 Develop digital tools and data analytics for pandemic and outbreak preparedness, including tracking genomics variations of SARS-CoV-2 and identifying new variants of concern	1. Broad uptake of viral Data Hubs across Europe deliver an order-of-magnitude increase in open viral variant detection and sharing.	No
	2. Infrastructure and quality workflows mobilised and shared to produce open , normative variant data that is incorporated into national and regional data systems and decision making.	No
Objective 5 Contribute to the Horizon Europe European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Partnership and	1. Guidelines and procedures for FAIR data management and access will be established, building on work of other guideline producing consortia such as the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), the 1Mio Genomes Initiative (1MG) and the Beyond One Million Genomes project (B1MG).	No

European Health Data Space (EHDS)	<p>2. Services, software, protocols, guidelines and other research objects that are openly accessible for reuse by the EOSC Association and the community at large as a foundation for European preparedness for infectious diseases, leveraging developments in EOSC-Life, SSHOC, EOSC-Future, EGI-ACE and other EOSC projects.</p>	Yes
	<p>3. Alignment (both policy and implementation routes) will have been achieved between the data governance strategies for routinely collected health data in the EHDS initiative, including the TEHDAS Joint Action and future EHDS Pilot Actions.</p>	No
	<p>4. To empower national centres to build capacity and train platform users and data providers (e.g., from life, social or health sciences), and with experts from across partner institutions collaborating to create training materials for the identified gaps, and to exchange experiences and knowledge.</p>	No

3. Introduction

3.1 Definitions

According to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹, **personal data** means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (“data subject”); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.

Under the GDPR, **special categories of personal data** include information revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, as well as genetic and biometric data used for identification. They also encompass *health-related data* and information concerning a person’s sex life or sexual orientation. Personal data belonging to these categories are often referred to as “**sensitive data**”.

Clinical trial data fall within these categories and as such different technical, organisational, ethical and legal measures need to be in place for enabling their secondary use. **Secondary use** of clinical trial data refers to their repurposing for objectives beyond the original drug development program or the initial goals of the clinical trial.

3.2 Secondary use of clinical trial data

Clinical trial data are invaluable resources for health research. Examples of secondary use of clinical trial data include:

- Allowing independent researchers to validate or scrutinise the original results.
- Testing new hypotheses that would otherwise require a new research study involving medical intervention on patients. These new hypotheses may aim to study other therapies or improve understanding of disease mechanisms.
- For regulatory purposes, such as to perform safety studies requested by authorities.
- For training purposes by providing real-world datasets to healthcare professionals or researchers for data analysis, interpretation, and clinical decision-making skills.
- Enhancing the efficiency, design, and methods of future clinical trials.

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

- Facilitating research collaborations (e.g., meta-analysis networks) that pool sensitive individual-level clinical trial data from multiple studies to aid in treatment evaluation and drug development.
- Developing and validating new healthcare technologies, such as algorithms based on Artificial Intelligence.

Different user personas may be interested in the secondary use of clinical trial data:

- Researchers aiming to perform additional analyses or explore new scientific questions.
- Attorneys seeking information for litigation purposes.
- Private companies, including potential competitors of the trial sponsor.
- Consultants with clients such as investment and financing companies and research organisations.
- Clinical trial participants who are interested in better understanding its results.
- Journalists covering specific treatments, conditions or clinical trials in general.
- Disease advocacy groups providing information to patients and their families or aiming to advance health research.
- Members of the public who want to learn more about the treatment or condition studied.
- Research Ethics Committees or scientific peer review committees reviewing a new or similar intervention to gain a comprehensive safety profile.
- Data and Safety Monitoring Boards/Data Monitoring Committees for other clinical trials, whose decisions to continue or terminate a trial may be influenced by results from a completed but unpublished trial.
- Educators using datasets for teaching purposes, such as biostatistics professors.
- Healthcare professionals for comparisons of treatments in different clinical trials without partially repeating these trials.

Since 2016, following the publication of the FAIR (standing for *Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable*) guiding principles for scientific data management², major

² Wilkinson M, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg I et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

stakeholders — including medical journal editors³, the healthcare industry⁴, and funding bodies⁵ — have been actively promoting the sharing and secondary use of clinical trial data. This movement aims not only to enhance data validity and build greater trust in scientific research but also to maximise the return on the original research investment. To facilitate researchers in the implementation of data sharing processes several stakeholders have also issued guidance documents, such as the World Health Organisation (WHO)⁶, the European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations (EFPIA)^{4,7,8} and the National Academy of Medicine⁹ (previously known as Institute of Medicine) in the United States of America (USA).

3.3 Enabling factors of clinical trial data sharing

To enable sharing of clinical trial data several factors must be in place along various stages of the clinical trial life-cycle⁹ (Figure 1):

- *Pre-trial*

Before a clinical trial begins, several pre-trial steps must be taken. The process typically starts with a literature review and feasibility analysis to confirm the research question is novel, valid, and practical to pursue. Considerations include participant availability, resources, and eventual timelines. Early engagement of key stakeholders such as academic institutions, pharmaceutical companies, regulators, ethics committees, and trial sites is crucial for securing support. Researchers then look for funding from grants or financial support from various organisations, preparing detailed proposals that include the study protocol and budget. **When data sharing for secondary use is planned, it is important to identify a suitable repository or to implement alternative arrangements and incorporate any associated costs into the budget.**

- *Trial set-up*

³ Taichman DB, Sahni P, Pinborg A et al. Data Sharing Statements for Clinical Trials: A Requirement of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors. JAMA (2017);317(24):2491-2492.

<https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2017.6514>

⁴ The PhRMA-EFPIA Principles for responsible clinical trial data sharing.

<https://www.efpia.eu/media/qndlduy/phrmaefpiaprinciplesforresponsibledatasharing2023.pdf>. Accessed on 09/08/2024

⁵ Kiley R, Peatfield T, Hansen J, Reddington F. Data Sharing from Clinical Trials - A Research Funder's Perspective. N Engl J Med. 2017;377(20):1990-1992. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMSb1708278>

⁶ Sharing and reuse of health-related data for research purposes: WHO policy and implementation guidance. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240044968>. Accessed on 09/08/2024

⁷ Clinical Trial Data Sharing Ecosystem.

<https://efpia.eu/media/636913/clinical-trial-data-sharing-ecosystem.pdf>. Accessed on 09/08/2024

⁸ Safeguards framework for secondary use of clinical trial data for scientific research.

<https://www.efpia.eu/media/413227/position-paper-safeguards-framework-for-secondary-use-of-clinical-trial-data-for-scientific-research-september-2019.pdf>. Accessed on 09/08/2024

⁹ Committee on Strategies for Responsible Sharing of Clinical Trial Data; Board on Health Sciences Policy; Institute of Medicine. Sharing Clinical Trial Data: Maximizing Benefits, Minimizing Risk. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US); 2015. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK285999/>

The clinical trial protocol, detailing the study design, endpoints, methodology, and procedures, is prepared and approved by a Research Ethics Committee (REC). Alongside this, the Statistical Analysis Plan (SAP) is developed to specify the statistical methods and analyses that will be applied to the collected data. **The protocol and the SAP are essential data objects for enabling meaningful secondary use of a clinical trial dataset. When data sharing is prospectively planned, this needs to be described within the trial protocol.** A **Data Management Plan (DMP)** is also established to ensure proper handling, storage, and security of trial data. **When data sharing is envisaged, the DMP can specify data discoverability mechanisms and/or include a section dedicated to data sharing and reuse.** The Case Report Form (CRF)¹⁰ is annotated to align with the protocol, and database specifications are created to guide the data collection process. **Promotion of interoperability by applying data and metadata standards (e.g., of the CDISC suite¹¹) is required in case of planned data sharing.** Trial registration is then completed on a public registry (e.g., ClinicalTrials.gov¹²). The **informed consent** process is outlined to educate participants about the trial's purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits, ensuring their voluntary participation and participant recruitment strategies are implemented targeting candidates that meet the study's inclusion and exclusion criteria. **When data sharing is foreseen, this has to be described in detail in the Patient Information Sheet and trial participants need to actively consent by opting in or out.** If adequate consent for secondary use has not been collected during the trial, other legal bases can enable sharing like “public interest” applicable in certain countries in the European Economic Area (EEA) (e.g., France) for research purposes or legitimate interest (Articles 6 and 9, GDPR). Finally, detailed plans for participant follow-up are established to collect necessary data throughout the trial's duration.

- *End of trial*

For the purposes of this deliverable, “*end of trial*” is defined as the point at which the study has concluded normally with participants no longer being examined or treated, or when the study is prematurely terminated¹³, halting recruitment and participant examination or treatment⁹. After the end of the trial, investigators and/or sponsors clean the data, derive additional variables, adjudicate endpoints, lock the dataset to create **the full analysable dataset** and carry out prespecified and additional analyses. A subset of this dataset is used to generate the tables, figures, and results for **scientific publications**. If the study aims to bring a new medical product to market, or before a new indication, formulation, or target

¹⁰ A CRF is a standardised paper or electronic questionnaire used by the sponsor/investigators of the clinical trial to collect data from each participant.

¹¹ <https://www.cdisc.org/>

¹² <https://clinicaltrials.gov/>

¹³ A study may be prematurely terminated for various reasons: a Data Monitoring Committee/Data and Safety Monitoring Board may recommend termination to the sponsor on the basis of interim monitoring for ethical and scientific reasons, or the sponsor may decide to terminate the study for ethical, scientific, or business reasons.

population can be approved for an intervention already on the market, an application to regulatory bodies and subsequent approval is needed.

- Data sharing

Data sharing for secondary use typically takes place after the clinical trial results have been published in scientific journals and regulatory submissions have been finalised. To facilitate the efficient and effective secondary use of the full analysable dataset, it is essential to share related data objects. These include trial protocols, Statistical Analysis Plans, consent form templates, result summaries, scientific publications, and any other document that can enhance the understanding of the dataset. Often, and in order to safeguard the privacy and confidentiality of the trial participants, **an additional step of pseudonymisation¹⁴/anonymisation¹⁵ to the already pseudonymised dataset is conducted.** Currently, **clinical trial data are shared either by using an appropriate thematic data repository or through secure file transfers by reaching out directly to the sponsor or Principal Investigator (PI).**

¹⁴ The GDPR defines pseudonymisation as “*the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person*” (Art. 4).

¹⁵ GDPR Recital 26 defines anonymous information, as “*... information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable*”. The GDPR does not apply to anonymised information.

Figure 1. Overview of the clinical trial life-cycle and all actions relevant to enable data sharing.

4. The clinical research Data Sharing Repository (crDSR)

In terms of thematic data repositories available to the clinical research community for data sharing, the most popular existing solutions are Vivli¹⁶ and ClinicalStudyDataRequest (CSDR)¹⁷. These initiatives, nevertheless, have typically been used and driven by industry and mainly by U.S.-based organisations. **To address this and provide an EU-based**

¹⁶ <https://vivli.org/>

¹⁷ <https://www.clinicalstudydatarequest.com/>

solution that would also cover the needs of academic stakeholders and Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs), the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN) partnered with the University of Oslo (UiO) to design, develop and implement a secure and ethically and legally compliant clinical research Data Sharing Repository (crDSR). This collaboration started within the EOSC-Life project¹⁸ and by the end of the project a repository demonstrator was provided. Collected pilot user feedback indicated that major improvements of usability aspects and correction of identified bugs were necessary before the tool can be widely offered to the clinical research community¹⁹. These technical improvements and additional features requested by users happened within the BY-COVID project.

In the crDSR, UiO provides a pre-existing Trusted Research Environment (TRE) for sensitive data storage and access control, called TSD, or the Service for Sensitive Data²⁰. ECRIN acts as the main repository interface with the research community - i.e. negotiating with those providing the material and those requesting access to it, managing the processes of both data transfer and data use, ensuring the provision of adequate metadata and monitoring compliance with legal and ethical obligations. To do so, ECRIN has developed an application (source code available in open access via Github^{21,22}) communicating with the TSD service that collects the metadata necessary for the findability, accessibility and reusability of the data objects according to the ECRIN Metadata Schema²³ and tracks the legal processes for making them available to secondary users. This application extends the current functionality of TSD with features specifically requested and expected by the clinical research community.

Figure 2 illustrates the homepage of the crDSR, which is available at <https://crdsr.ecriin.org/>.

¹⁸ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

¹⁹ Contrino S, Felder G, Ohmann C et al. (2023). EOSC-Life Report about use and user satisfaction of the COVID-19 repository, including a maintenance and sustainability plan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7836812>

²⁰ <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/>

²¹ <https://github.com/ecrin-github/rms-portal-new>

²² <https://github.com/ecrin-github/esbs-django>

²³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368709>

crDSR

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The clinical research Data Sharing Repository is capable of holding any type of digital object – data sets, documents, media file etc- in a secure research environment (TRE). The repository collects the metadata necessary for the Findability of the objects, promoting data sharing in clinical research.

Figure 2. The homepage of the crDSR.

There are two main processes supported by the crDSR:

- the **Data Transfer Process (DTP)**, when clinical study material is provided to the repository (see for more details Appendix 1); depicted schematically in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The Data Transfer Process. The Data Object Provider completes in the crDSR information about the study, the data objects that will be shared and the access modes and prerequisites. This information is harmonised according to the ECRIN Metadata Schema for clinical research²³. The Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) between the Data Object Provider and ECRIN is negotiated and upon its signature the data objects are transferred to TSD for setting up access modalities. Once upload is completed the data objects are advertised as available in the crDSR. Blue: Actions carried out by the Data Object Provider. Green: Actions carried out by ECRIN. Yellow: Actions carried out by TSD.

- the **Data Use Process (DUP)**, when clinical study material is accessed for secondary use; depicted schematically in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The Data Use Process. The Secondary User needs to provide a list of the data objects requested, the reason for the request and information on secondary users. ECRIN checks the request for eligibility according to the criteria set by the Data Object Provider and, if eligible, initiates the Data Use Agreement (DUA) signature process with the Secondary User. Upon signature, TSD sends to the Secondary User credentials for TSD and information on access. Blue: Actions carried out by the Secondary User. Green: Actions carried out by ECRIN. Yellow: Actions carried out by TSD.

The transfer of data objects to the crDSR is governed by a **Data Transfer Agreement (DTA)** signed between the Data Object Provider and ECRIN, which covers the transfer of all data objects, including, but not limited to, datasets. Each DTA includes an appendix describing the data objects to be transferred to the repository, and the access arrangements desired for each of them. Further details (e.g., prerequisites for secondary use, categorisation as anonymised or pseudonymised) are required for objects under controlled access. For data objects under controlled access, the requester organisations are asked to sign a **Data Use Agreement (DUA)** with ECRIN on behalf of the secondary users. The DUAs constrain the use of the controlled access objects, typically explicitly prohibiting any attempt to re-identify individuals within a dataset, stipulating that datasets should be stored securely and destroyed after the approved data access period expires, and requiring that the providers and repository are notified of the results of the secondary use. Access can only take place *in-situ*, within the TSD TRE. Commonly used data analysis software is pre-installed, including Amnesia²⁴, Gitea²⁵, R²⁶, Stata²⁷, Perl²⁸, Python²⁹ and SPSS³⁰. Other software can be made available to users upon request.

The current version of the Data Sharing Policy of the crDSR is provided in Appendix 2.

²⁴ <https://amnesia.openaire.eu/>

²⁵ <https://gitea.com/>

²⁶ <https://www.r-project.org/>

²⁷ <https://www.stata.com/>

²⁸ <https://www.perl.org/>

²⁹ <https://www.python.org/>

³⁰ <https://www.ibm.com/spss>

5. crDSR pilot use cases

This section describes pilot use cases for the crDSR, approached during the BY-COVID project.

5.1 The VACCELERATE project

The VACCELERATE project³¹ is funded by the European Commission's Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (HERA) incubator³², which focuses on activities to enhance future pandemic preparedness, similar to the United States' Biomedical Advanced Research and Development Authority (BARDA)³³. Launched in February 2021 with a duration of 36 months, VACCELERATE aims to establish a clinical research network to coordinate and conduct COVID-19 vaccine trials. The consortium, led by the University Hospital Cologne (UHC) in Germany, currently consists of 31 national partners across 18 EU Member States and 5 countries associated with the EU Horizon 2020 research program.

The network addresses critical research questions that arose during the pandemic through the implementation of three clinical trials:

- **EU-COVAT-1 AGED:** A multinational, phase 2, randomised, adaptive trial evaluating the immunogenicity and reactogenicity of different COVID-19 vaccines in older adults (≥ 75) who have already been vaccinated against SARS-CoV-2.
- **EU-COVAT-2 BOOSTAVAC:** An international, multicenter, phase 2, randomised, adaptive trial to assess the need for, optimal timing of, and immunogenicity of administering a fourth homologous mRNA vaccine dose against SARS-CoV-2 in the general population (18+ years) who have already received the BNT162b2 vaccine.
- **EU-COVPT-1 COVACC:** A phase 2, comparative, randomised trial evaluating the impact of a reduced COVID-19 mRNA vaccination regimen on immunological responses and reactogenicity in paediatric subjects with prior SARS-CoV-2 immunity.

Within the BY-COVID project, ECRIN collaborated with the EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial and its sponsor, UHC, to make the clinical study's Individual Participant Data (IPD) and associated data objects available for secondary use via the crDSR. Collaboration with the EU-COVAT-2 BOOSTAVAC and EU-COVPT-1 COVACC trials was not possible due to the timelines for their completion, which go beyond the BY-COVID duration.

³¹ <https://vaccelerate.eu/>

³² https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/qanda_21_4733

³³ <https://aspr.hhs.gov/AboutASPR/ProgramOffices/BARDA/Pages/default.aspx>

5.1.1 The EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial

EU-COVAT-1 AGED is a multinational, phase 2, randomised clinical trial that investigates the immunogenicity and reactogenicity of a second booster dose of either BNT162b2³⁴ (30 µg) or mRNA-1273³⁵ (100 µg) in adults aged 75 and older. EU-COVAT-1-AGED has been registered in ClinicalTrials.gov with identifier NCT05160766³⁶.

Following approval from the responsible ethics committee on November 8, 2021, and regulatory approval from the Paul-Ehrlich-Institut on October 20, 2021, enrollment for the trial commenced in November 2021 at a single centre in Cologne, Germany. This initial stage, referred to as Part A, aimed to investigate the effects of a third COVID-19 vaccination dose. A total of 53 participants were recruited for Part A, and the results are detailed in a dedicated publication³⁷. However, due to changes in public health policy at the time, which recommended a third COVID-19 vaccination dose for the population at risk (including elderly), the trial protocol had to be amended, leading to the early termination of Part A.

Part B of the trial focused on investigating the effects of a fourth COVID-19 vaccination dose. It received full approval on January 21, 2022, and was conducted in a multicenter setting as part of the VACCELERATE consortium. The trial sites included Cologne, Frankfurt, and Hannover (Germany); Vilnius (Lithuania); Bergen (Norway); and Barcelona, Córdoba, Madrid, and San Sebastián (Spain). Enrollment for Part B was prematurely closed on December 6, 2022, following the sponsor's decision due to further public health policy changes favouring variant-adapted vaccines. A total of 270 participants were recruited for Part B, with the results reported in detail in a second publication³⁸. Figure 5 schematically depicts the course of the EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial conduct.

³⁴ Also referred to as Comirnaty or BioNTech/Pfizer

³⁵ Also referred to as Spikevax or Moderna

³⁶ <https://clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT05160766?term=NCT05160766&rank=1>

³⁷ Neuhann JM, Stemler J, Carcas AJ et al. Immunogenicity and reactogenicity of a first booster with BNT162b2 or full-dose mRNA-1273: a randomised VACCELERATE trial in adults ≥75 years (EU-COVAT1). *Vaccine* 2023;41:7166–75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vaccine.2023.10.029>

³⁸ Stemler J, Yeghiazaryan L, Stephan C et al. Immunogenicity, reactogenicity, and safety of a second booster with BNT162b2 or full-dose mRNA-1273: A randomized VACCELERATE trial in adults aged ≥75 years (EU-COVAT-1-AGED Part B). *Int J Infect Dis.* 2024 Sep;146:107161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijid.2024.107161>

Figure 5. Course of the EU-COVAT-1 AGED clinical trial conduct. Adapted from the Supplementary Material in ³⁸.

Due to the constantly evolving public health policies during the COVID-19 pandemic, the trial protocol had to undergo several amendments, complicating participant recruitment and causing significant delays in the trial. Consequently, the initially planned enrollment target of 550 participants was not achieved, and the groups being compared fell short of the calculated statistical sample size. Additionally, data on immunogenicity at the 12-month mark have not yet been reported.

More information on the EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial inclusion criteria and endpoints is provided in Appendix 3.

5.1.2 Status of the EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial data sharing

Due to the constant changes in the public health policy recommendations and the subsequent delays in the EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial, the data sharing process has not yet been completed. Nevertheless, and as highlighted in section 3.3, in order to share data from a clinical trial several steps need to be taken at different stages. The steps taken to allow data sharing in the EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial are listed below.

- ***Pre-trial:*** Sufficient **budget** allocated for data sharing activities to UHC, ECRIN and UiO within the VACCELERATE and BY-COVID projects.
- ***Trial set-up:*** Data sharing via the crDSR is explicitly mentioned in the trial master **protocol**. More precisely the following addition was made:

“In line with the EU data sharing policy, individual patient-level data will be shared with the scientific community (either as anonymised or pseudonymised datasets), while maintaining the integrity and privacy of the trial participants and in compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation and national or local rules. Data and other trial documents should be made available through an appropriate data

repository, helping to ensure that the data objects are properly prepared, are available in the longer term, are stored securely and are subject to rigorous governance. It is planned to use the COVID-19 repository for individual participant data from clinical trials developed within the EU-project EOSC-Life. The terms and conditions of data transfers to a repository and the data sharing process shall be subject to specific data processing agreements to be established between the concerned parties as well as to a specific data sharing plan, where the details are specified.”

In addition, **a specific Patient Information Sheet and Informed Consent Form for Further Research**³⁹ were developed to enable legal and ethical sharing of the clinical trial dataset using the crDSR.

- *End of trial*: So far, **two Open Access publications** reporting the analysed results of the trial have been produced as part of the VACCELERATE project^{37,38}.
- *Data sharing*: A **Data Transfer Agreement template**⁴⁰ has been produced and is currently under negotiation with the clinical trial sponsor to identify terms and conditions for secondary data use of the clinical trial dataset and other associated data objects. In addition, discussion on further **pseudonymisation / anonymisation** of the clinical trial dataset prior to sharing has been initiated. A challenge faced by the partners is that clinical trial data centres do not have pseudonymisation / anonymisation expertise for secondary use purposes. As such, an external anonymisation expert had to be approached to guide the data managers on the application of adequate anonymisation steps that will safeguard the privacy and confidentiality of the data subjects. The step of anonymisation is still ongoing.

The **Data Transfer Process** of the EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial data objects within the crDSR has been initiated (Figure 6) and the relevant metadata pages for the study (Figure 7) and data object description (Figure 8) started to be populated. The screenshots below showcase the system functionality. However, until the finalisation of the contractual agreements with the clinical trial sponsor, the list of data objects and the access type per data object is still prone to changes (Appendix 4).

The timeline for completing all the data sharing steps for the EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial is December 2024.

³⁹ https://docs.google.com/document/d/1S4xPM5I-pnOTYPcOhqHHZLevsWFu_9hr/edit

⁴⁰ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1wvpOmWxIaIIggOVflr93Vjp8YpLYAIAk/edit>

The screenshot displays the 'Data Transfer Details' page in the crDSR: Data Sharing Repository (v1.5.0). The page title is 'Data Transfer Details' and the identifier is 'DTP-0002-EU-VACCELERATE'. At the top right, there are buttons for 'Edit', 'PDF', 'JSON', and 'Back'. Below the title, there are three tabs: 'Overview' (selected), 'Linked Objects and People', and 'Controlled Access Details'. The 'Overview' tab shows the following information:

- Organisation***: Universitätsklinikum Köln
- Display Name***: DTP-0002-EU-VACCELERATE
- Status**: Agreement

Below this information, there are four steps in the data transfer process:

- Set up of studies, objects, users**: Completed (indicated by a green checkmark).
- Agreement preparation**: In progress (indicated by a yellow warning icon).
- Quality checks of objects**: Not started.
- Transfer of objects to TSD**: Not started.

Timeline information:

- Setup Started**: 2024/09/03
- Setup Completed**: 2024/09/03

A 'NEXT STEP' button is located below the timeline. Below the process steps, there is an 'Agreement Details' section with the following fields:

- Conforms To Default**: No
- Variations**: (empty field)
- DTA File Path**: (empty field)
- Repository Signatory 1**: (empty field)
- Repository Signatory 2**: (empty field)
- Provider Signatory 1**: (empty field)
- Provider Signatory 2**: (empty field)

At the bottom, there is a 'Notes' section with a text area.

Figure 6. Data Transfer Process for the EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial initiated within the crDSR (screenshot).

crDSR: Data Sharing Repository
v1.5.0

Study Details

Assessing Immune Response of Different COVID-19 Vaccines in Older Adults

Edit
PDF
JSON
Back

Study Id
DSRS-2

Title *
Assessing Immune Response of Different COVID-19 Vaccines in Older Adults

Organisation *
Universitätsklinikum Köln

Status *
Active, not recruiting

Type *
Interventional

Start Month
11

Start Year *
2021

Brief Description

This is a randomised controlled, adaptive, multicentre Phase II protocol evaluating different booster strategies in individuals aged 75 years and older already vaccinated against SARS-CoV-2. Part B of this trial foresees testing of different vaccines as a 4th vaccination dose (second booster) for comparative assessment of their immunogenicity and safety against SARSCoV-2 wild-type and variants in the elderly, a usually neglected population. Additional vaccines and extended follow-up visits can be added through amendments of this sub-protocol. As stated in the EU-COVAT master protocol, this trial, i.e., the EU-COVAT-1_AGED study, implements a specific safety monitoring strategy. Cohorts and arms can be withdrawn or added as deemed necessary according to the criteria specified in this protocol.

Data Sharing Statement

No statement provided

Study Gender Eligibility

All

Min Age
75

Study Enrollment

323

Max Age
Years

Study identifier(s)

- Trial registry ID: 2021-004526-29
- Trial registry ID: NCT05160766

Study title(s)

- A multinational, phase 2, randomised, adaptive protocol to assess immune response and side effects of different COVID-19 vaccines in older adults
- A Multinational, Phase 2, Randomised, Adaptive Protocol to Evaluate Immunogenicity and Reactogenicity of Different COVID-19 Vaccines in Older Adults

Study feature(s)

- Allocation Type**
Randomised
- Intervention Model**
Parallel assignment
- Masking**
None (Open Label)

Figure 7. Study page in the crDSR completed for the EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial (screenshot).

 crDSR: Data Sharing Repository v1.5.3 ☰

Data Objects + New data object

Organisation köl

Study ID	Title	Organisation	Type	Linked study	Actions
DSRO-9	Biobank Concept	Universitätsklinikum Köln	Definitions	DSRS-2	
DSRO-11	Case Report Form	Universitätsklinikum Köln	Data collection forms	DSRS-2	
DSRO-8	Data Management Plan	Universitätsklinikum Köln	Data management plan	DSRS-2	
DSRO-14	Database Specification	Universitätsklinikum Köln	Database specification	DSRS-2	
DSRO-18	Individual Participant Data	Universitätsklinikum Köln	Individual participant data	DSRS-2	
DSRO-7	Master trial protocol	Universitätsklinikum Köln	Study protocol	DSRS-2	
DSRO-12	Patient Information and Consent Form	Universitätsklinikum Köln	Informed consent forms	DSRS-2	
DSRO-15	Publication Results Part A	Universitätsklinikum Köln	Journal article	DSRS-2	
DSRO-16	Publication Results Part B	Universitätsklinikum Köln	Journal article	DSRS-2	
DSRO-13	Subject diary	Universitätsklinikum Köln	Data collection forms	DSRS-2	
DSRO-10	Summary Of Product Characteristics Comirnaty	Universitätsklinikum Köln	Definitions	DSRS-2	
DSRO-17	Summary Of Product Characteristics Spikevax	Universitätsklinikum Köln	Definitions	DSRS-2	
DSRO-6	Trial Protocol	Universitätsklinikum Köln	Study protocol	DSRS-2	

Items per page: 25 1 – 13 of 13 < >

Figure 8. Data Objects page in the crDSR completed for the EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial (screenshot).

5.2 Data sharing in other COVID-19 clinical studies

Once the crDSR was ready for use, and given the delays in data sharing for the VACCELERATE EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial, **other candidate COVID-19 clinical studies potentially willing to share data with secondary users had to be identified.**

In December 2015, ClinicalTrials.gov introduced two optional fields to its protocol registration and results system (PRS) to address the sharing of IPD: “Plan to Share IPD” and “Available IPD/Information Type”. A research study examining the use of these fields on ClinicalTrials.gov found potential confusion regarding the definitions of “IPD” and “sharing”, as well as inconsistencies in the responses provided by the trial stakeholders⁴¹. To clarify these issues, ClinicalTrials.gov added more specific subfields to the IPD Sharing Statement section in June 2017⁴². This updated section now includes a primary statement on the plan to share IPD (yes, no, undecided), followed by detailed information if “yes” is selected, such as “Plan Description”, “IPD Sharing”, “Supporting Information”, “Time Frame”, “Access Criteria”, and “URL”. The addition of these structured subfields aimed to facilitate clearer and more comprehensive IPD-sharing plans.

These advancements have provided an opportunity to research groups, including the ECRIN BY-COVID team to **quantify data sharing in clinical studies**. For the quantification of COVID-19 studies willing to share IPD the BY-COVID partners employed the ECRIN clinical research MetaData Repository (crMDR) that is developed within BY-COVID WP2 and available at <https://crmdr.ecrin.org/>. Figure 9 lists the quantification studies of clinical study data sharing conducted by different research teams.

Researcher, year	Time	Resource	Study type	“Yes” in DSS field of study registration (%)
Bergeris et al., 2018 ⁴¹	January 2016 to August 2017	CT.gov	Interventional trial	10.9%
Tan et al., 2021 ⁴³	December 2018 to November 2019	ANZTR	Interventional trial	22%
Statham et al., 2020 ⁴⁴	January 2018 to June 2018	CT.gov	Interventional trial	5.5%
Li et al., 2021 ⁴⁵	Before 30 June	CT.gov	COVID-19,	15.7% and 17.3% after

⁴¹ Bergeris A, Tse T, Zarin DA. Trialists' Intent to Share Individual Participant Data as Disclosed at ClinicalTrials.gov. JAMA. 2018; 319(4):406-408. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2017.20581>

⁴² <https://prsinfo.clinicaltrials.gov/>

⁴³ Tan AC, Askie LM, Hunter KE et al. Data sharing-trialists' plans at registration, attitudes, barriers and facilitators: A cohort study and cross-sectional survey. Res Synth Methods. 2021;12(5):641-657. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1500>

⁴⁴ Statham EE, White SA, Sonwane B et al. Primed to comply: Individual participant data sharing statements on ClinicalTrials.gov. PLoS One. 2020 Feb 18;15(2):e0226143. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0226143>

⁴⁵ Li, R., von Isenburg, M., Levenstein, M. et al. COVID-19 trials: declarations of data sharing intentions at trial registration and at publication. Trials 22, 153 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13063-021-05104-z>

	2020		interventional trial	re-classification
Larsson et al., 2022 ⁴⁶	Up to September 2021	CT.gov	COVID-19, interventional trial	15% and 15.7% after re-classification
Merson et al., 2022 ⁴⁷	January 2019 to December 2020	WHO ICTRP	Registered study	4.8%
Xu et al., 2020 ⁴⁸	Up to December 2018	WHO ICTRP	Global registration of studies sponsored by China	Around 5%
ECRIN BY-COVID team, 2022 ⁴⁹	Up to January 2023	ECRIN crMDR	COVID-19, registered study	16.55%

Figure 9. Studies investigating the willingness to share IPD in clinical trial registries (adapted from the BY-COVID study published in⁴⁹).

In total, the ECRIN BY-COVID team identified 7618 COVID-19 registered studies with a completed DSS field, 1261 out of which had answered “yes” (16.55%). This finding is similar to the studies from Li⁴⁵ and Larson⁴⁶. **However, it is worth noting that between declared and actual data sharing a wide gap exists^{41, 50}.**

5.2.1 Developing a classification system for DSS

What was still missing in the literature was a study that investigates whether the detailed DSS fields provide clear instructions to secondary users. **We therefore designed a study with the primary objective of developing and evaluating a classification system for DSS of registered trials, characterising the degree and type of willingness for data sharing, and the extent and clarity of supporting information⁴⁹.**

The resulting classification system and the definition of terms are presented in Figure 10.

⁴⁶ Larson K, Sim I, von Isenburg M, et al. COVID-19 interventional trials: analysis of data sharing intentions during a time of pandemic. *Contemporary Clinical Trials*. 2022;115:106709.

⁴⁷ Merson L, Ndwandwe D, Malinga T, et al. Promotion of data sharing needs more than an emergency: an analysis of trends across clinical trials registered on the International Clinical Trials Registry Platform [version 1; peer review: 2 approved]. *Wellcome Open Res*. 2022;7:101.

⁴⁸ Xu Y, Dong M, Liu X. Characteristics and trends of clinical studies primarily sponsored by China in WHO primary registries between 2009 and 2018: a cross-sectional survey. *BMJ Open*. 2020;10:e037262.

⁴⁹ Ohmann, C., Panagiotopoulou, M., Canham, S. et al. An assessment of the informative value of data sharing statements in clinical trial registries. *BMC Med Res Methodol* 24, 61 (2024).

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-024-02168-8>

⁵⁰ Danchev V, Min Y, Borghi J et al. Evaluation of Data Sharing After Implementation of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors Data Sharing Statement Requirement. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2021;4(1):e2033972. doi: 10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.33972.

Classification	Definition
Unclear	DSS not understood. Either the statement makes no sense (e.g., is not coherent English), or IPD is not mentioned at all, or IPD is mentioned but the intention to share or not share is not made clear, even in the vaguely positive sense described by 'vaguely positive' below. N.B. Responses that indicate that 'demographic data' or 'clinical data' or similar will be shared are ambiguous – the data could be summary tables rather than IPD. Unless clarified elsewhere in the DSS, therefore, such responses fall into this category. In all cases the intention, or not, to share IPD for secondary use is simply unknown.
No sharing	DSS states or implies that there will be no sharing of IPD. Different specific reasons may be provided. Usually an explicit statement is made (e.g. "transfer of data to third parties excluded") but sometimes a reference is made to an implied reason for not sharing ("patients' confidentiality"). DSS that refer only to sharing of aggregate or results data, or only to publication of a journal paper are also assumed to fall into the 'no sharing' category.
No plans	DSS states that there are currently no plans regarding IPD sharing, or a decision has not yet been made. Usually, an explicit statement but may be implicit in statements such as "need to consult with collaborators / participants". N.B. "Not yet planned..." would fall into this category, while "not planned..." would be classified as 'no sharing'.
Vaguely positive	Vaguely positive. DSS states or implies that there will be some degree of IPD sharing, but no details are given or sharing appears limited, e.g. "To be made available at a later date". This is the weakest of the positive statements. Sometimes the intention is made clear but the details are not yet available – e.g. "The investigators will be sharing the data, but the management plan is being designed."
By request	DSS states that IPD can be obtained by request, usually as an explicit statement, occasionally just as an email address. Few further details about the access process are provided and there are no additional prerequisites identified (other than, sometimes, the fact that a Data Use Agreement must be signed). The contact person is usually the investigator, sometimes the sponsor, but the role may not be stated.
Complex	DSS states or implies that IPD will be available and describes or references a more complex regime than a simple request. Common additional requirements are for requests to be reviewed by a data access or trial committee, for the applicants to have an approved protocol, or to follow a named procedure set out in a document or web page. These DSS are therefore positive but provide more detail than simply stating the data can be requested.
Via Storage	DSS explicitly states that IPD will be transferred to a specific data repository – may be general, specific to clinical research or institutional - which would normally be named. The data repository (e.g., CSDR, Vivli, or Yoda) should have its own access policies and procedures, and not be just a repository for publicly available documents (e.g., Zenodo). This is a version of the 'complex+' category above, but with the additional requirements partially provided by repository systems.

Figure 10. Classification system for DSS developed by the BY-COVID partners (taken from⁴⁹).

Subsequently, the classification system was applied to a random sample of 200 COVID-19 clinical studies (both completed and ongoing studies were considered) with explicit⁵¹ Data Sharing Statements identified via the ECRIN crMDR. The objective was to see how useful this classification can be in practice to guide secondary users towards studies with higher possibility of data sharing and clear instructions for the data sharing processes.

Our analysis showed that in 13% of the COVID-19 clinical studies the DSS were unclear, 14% were not really willing to share individual-level data, 11% had no specific plans at the time of the registration, 16% were vague, 30% were providing defined request conditions for data access, 8% were providing a defined storage location and 11% had rather complex access conditions (e.g., such as approval by a Data Access Committee)⁴⁹.

Classification	Specification	Number of cases
Unclear	-	13% (25/200)
No data sharing	-	14% (27/200)
No plans	-	11% (21/200)
Yes	<i>Vague</i>	16% (31/200)
	<i>Defined request conditions</i>	30% (60/200)
	<i>Defined storage location</i>	8% (15/200)
	<i>Complex conditions</i>	11% (21/200)
Total	-	200

Figure 11. Classification of the 200 COVID-19 clinical studies based on experts' consensus (taken from ⁴⁹).

The application of the classification system to the 200 clinical studies allowed the BY-COVID partners to provide an internal inventory of selected COVID-19 studies classified according to the likelihood of sharing data for secondary use⁵².

5.2.2 Follow up on Data Sharing Statements

From the inventory of 200 COVID-19 clinical studies⁵², the BY-COVID partners **selected 131 studies that appeared more likely to share IPD and had not yet identified a data repository or sharing platform**. These studies were contacted with a follow-up survey to clarify data sharing requirements and prerequisites and to gauge whether the clinical trial sponsors or PIs would be open to collaborating with the crDSR and make the datasets of their study available for secondary use.

⁵¹ Definition of explicit: i) for ClinicalTrials.gov studies, as those that provided more details than the simple initial response of "Yes", "No" or "Undecided", ii) for data from other registries, as those that had any response at all, as a free text statement

⁵² https://docs.google.com/document/d/1hI65iwiuz-I39NP3wXJOt-TJa7EM9ISc/edit?usp=drive_web&ouid=116146004604654679354&rtoref=true

The survey was prepared using Microsoft Forms and was run from 26/07/2024 until 01/09/2024. The survey form can be found in Appendix 5.

Our initial identification of the sponsor or PI focused on the contact information provided in the clinical study registry pages. **While the name and affiliation of the sponsor or PI are often listed, their email addresses are frequently missing. As a result, even for studies that express a willingness to share data, potential secondary users must conduct a manual search to find the email addresses of the listed contact points responsible for the study.**

Furthermore, out of the 131 studies we contacted for the survey, 13 (~10%) were unreachable due to email errors, such as people retiring or changing jobs. While this is common, clinical study registry pages and DSS are often not updated to reflect such changes, making it difficult for secondary users to contact studies that claim to be open to data sharing. Consequently, our survey successfully reached 113 studies (~90%), of which 28 completed the survey, resulting in a response rate of ~25%.

Status of the clinical studies that were surveyed

The first question of our survey consisted of clarifying the current status of the clinical study and the respondents could select one of the following:

- *“Not yet recruiting”*
- *“Recruiting”*
- *“Active, not recruiting”*
- *“Withdrawn / Suspended / Terminated”*
- *“Completed”*

Of the 28 clinical studies that responded to the survey, 24 (~86%) were completed (Figure 12). This is not surprising as the survey aimed to understand the data sharing options implemented by the clinical study. **Studies that are not yet recruiting or that were “Withdrawn / Suspended / Terminated” for any reason (such as the interest towards COVID-19 diminishing over time) were less likely to consider participating in the BY-COVID survey** (which can also explain the low ~25% response rate).

Figure 12. Current status of the 28 COVID-19 clinical studies that responded to the survey.

Status of IPD sharing so far

The 28 survey respondents were then asked whether IPD sharing had already occurred, considering they all had a positive DSS in their trial registry. We expect that the demand for the secondary use of COVID-19 datasets likely peaked between 2019 and 2022. However, only 8 of the 28 respondents (~28.5%) reported having shared IPD with potential secondary users outside their institution. This indicates that, despite expressing willingness to share IPD, 20 (~71.5%) clinical studies did not share data, even during the peak of the pandemic.

Current willingness to share IPD

Next, we aimed to determine if the 28 COVID-19 clinical studies were still willing to share IPD with secondary users. Of the respondents, 21 out of 28 (~75%) remained open to sharing their clinical study data. In contrast, 6 respondents were no longer willing, and 1 was undecided.

Figure 13. Number of COVID-19 clinical studies that are still willing to share IPD with secondary users.

For the 6 clinical studies that responded "No" to the question "Are you still willing to share IPD with researchers outside your institution?", a follow-up question was asked to understand what had changed since their initial positive DSS declaration. These respondents were asked to list the main reasons for their decision. The responses indicated that a major reason (selected 3 times) is ethical and legal issues (e.g., uncertainty about the legal basis for sharing and compatibility with informed consent). Of equal importance is the lack of time and resources to manage data sharing (e.g., insufficient personnel or other institutional priorities at the end of a clinical trial) (option selected 3 times). Additionally, the respondents raised the importance of credit attribution and fears of data misuse or scooping by other teams (option selected 2 times), while 2 other reasons were mentioned including the study being withdrawn without recruitment and not receiving data re-use requests, finding the effort justifiable. Notably, none of the respondents indicated data-related issues (e.g., organising data in a presentable or reusable way) as a reason for not sharing IPD.

Figure 14. Main reasons for not sharing IPD according to the 6 respondents that claimed that they would no longer be willing to share IPD with secondary users (*multiple choice question*).

Data access process for IPD sharing

The next question was directed at the 22 clinical studies still willing or potentially willing to share IPD with secondary users, aiming to determine whether they had implemented concrete data access steps to enable effective secondary use. Surprisingly, despite expressing a willingness to share IPD, 8 (~36%) of these studies had not established any data access process. 7 studies (~32%) stated that data access occurs through email contact with the sponsor/PI, followed by file transfer. Only 1 study (~4.5%) reported using an institutional data repository for sharing their datasets, while 5 studies (~23%) utilised an external data repository (such as OSF⁵³, Vivli⁵⁴ and the UK Data Service Archive⁵⁵). Additionally, 1 study (~4.5%) selected "None of the above" but did not provide further details.

Figure 15. Different data access options for the COVID-19 clinical studies that claimed willingness to still share IPD.

Specific conditions for sharing IPD via a data repository

All 28 respondents were asked to specify the conditions under which they would be willing to share their study's IPD using a data repository. This question aimed to outline the prerequisites that the crDSR must fulfil to appeal to the clinical research community, which is often hesitant to adopt data-sharing policies. The most critical condition for data providers is the assurance of proper credit attribution to the team that generated the data. Additionally, it is important that any services provided by a data repository remain free for the data provider and that there is adequate ethical and legal support. Discussions with several clinical trial sponsors/PIs have highlighted a lack of institutional support on ethical and legal matters, as well as insufficient expertise regarding secondary data use. Less important considerations included having the data repository manage re-use requests and providing anonymisation/pseudonymisation services. Some respondents also noted that

⁵³ <https://osf.io/>

⁵⁴ <https://vivli.org/>

⁵⁵ <https://reshare.ukdataservice.ac.uk/855905/>

funding should be available to data providers to cover the time and effort required to make their data accessible for secondary use through a repository.

Figure 16. Specific conditions for making IPD and associated data objects available via a data repository.

Interest in collaboration with crDSR

An additional goal of the survey was to identify COVID-19 studies that could collaborate with the crDSR, alongside VACCELERATE, to explore additional use cases. The survey asked the 28 respondents whether they would be interested in collaborating with the crDSR to share their study's IPD. 7 respondents expressed a definite interest ("Yes"), 16 were uncertain ("Maybe"), and 5 were not interested ("No"). For those who were open to further discussion, 18 respondents provided their contact information to explore potential collaboration with the crDSR.

Would you be interested in collaborating with the crDSR to share the IPD of your study?

Figure 17. Number of clinical studies that wish to explore a collaboration with the crDSR to make their clinical study available to secondary users.

6. Conclusions

The secondary use of clinical trial data allows for its repurposing beyond the original research objectives, enabling activities such as validation of initial results, hypothesis testing, regulatory safety studies, improving clinical trial design, and developing new healthcare technologies. The promotion of data sharing by key organisations (e.g., WHO, EFPIA) and the adoption of the FAIR principles has been crucial in advancing the availability of such data, enhancing transparency, and maximising research investment returns.

Effective data sharing in clinical trials requires careful planning throughout the trial lifecycle. This includes *pre-trial* activities such as engaging stakeholders, securing funding, and selecting an appropriate data repository; *trial set-up* tasks like developing protocols that specify data sharing, implementing good data management practices, and establishing informed consent procedures; and actions at the *end of the trial* such as publishing results in open access journals. The *data sharing* step involves making IPD and related documents (e.g., protocols, Statistical Analysis Plans, consent forms) available to secondary users, usually after the trial results have been published and regulatory submissions completed. At this step, privacy protection measures, such as pseudonymisation or anonymisation, are applied, and data is transferred to thematic repositories.

ECRIN and UiO have delivered the clinical research Data Sharing Repository (crDSR, <https://crdsr.ecriin.org/>) to offer a secure and ethically and legally compliant, EU platform for sharing clinical research data. The crDSR supports two main processes: the Data Transfer Process, for uploading clinical study materials to the repository, and the Data Use Process, for accessing data for secondary research. Both processes are governed by agreements (Data Transfer Agreement and Data Use Agreement) that outline the terms for data sharing and use, including privacy safeguards, security measures, and conditions for

secondary use. Data access is controlled within the TRE of TSD, which provides pre-installed analysis tools.

In the BY-COVID project, the crDSR is being piloted for the data sharing of the VACCELERATE-funded clinical trial EU-COVAT-1 AGED. The EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial is a multinational, phase 2, randomised, adaptive trial evaluating the immunogenicity and reactogenicity of different COVID-19 vaccines in older adults (≥ 75) who have already been vaccinated against SARS-CoV-2. **The EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial has faced delays in the data sharing process due to evolving public health policies (e.g., recommendations for a third vaccination dose to high risk populations, recommendations for variant-specific vaccines), but some of the data sharing actions in the different stages of the clinical trial life cycle have been achieved.** These include ensuring adequate data sharing budget allocation, clinical trial protocol modifications for data sharing, and the development of specific legal and ethical documents. In addition, the Data Transfer Process using the crDSR has been initiated and the submission of metadata describing the study and the data objects to be shared has been nearly completed. A Data Transfer Agreement is currently under negotiation. The aim is to finalise all data sharing steps by December 2024.

Alternative COVID-19 clinical studies for data sharing via the crDSR had to be identified. This is possible thanks to policy changes making the provision of DSS obligatory elements of the trial registration. **The BY-COVID team used the ECRIN clinical research MetaData Repository (crMDR, <https://crmdr.ecriin.org/>) and identified a total of 7618 COVID-19 registered studies with a completed DSS field, 1261 out of which had answered “yes” (16.55%) to data sharing.** This percentage is confirmed by literature.

The BY-COVID team developed a classification system to evaluate the clarity and usefulness of Data Sharing Statements (DSS) for secondary users. This system was applied to a sample of 200 COVID-19 clinical studies with explicit DSS, and the findings were published in BMC Medical Research Methodology. From these 200 studies, the BY-COVID partners identified 131 that seemed more likely to share IPD but had not yet selected a data repository or sharing platform. These studies were then contacted with **a follow-up survey to clarify data sharing requirements and explore whether the clinical trial sponsors or principal investigators would be willing to collaborate with the crDSR and provide their datasets for secondary use.**

The survey uncovered significant obstacles for secondary users, including **difficulties in contacting sponsors or principal investigators due to missing email addresses in clinical trial registry pages.** Despite ~71.5% of respondents not sharing their data during the pandemic, around 75% of the respondents declared to remain still open to data sharing. **The respondents that are not willing anymore to share IPD cite issues like lack of time, adequate personnel, and ethical or legal uncertainties.**

The majority of the respondents that declared willingness to share data have either not implemented any formal data access process (~36%) or rely on e-mail exchanges and

file transfers (~32%). In order for respondents to use a data repository in their data sharing process they stressed the importance of proper credit attribution mechanisms, free repository services for data providers, and provision of ethical and legal support.

The majority of the surveyed clinical studies declared an interest (“Yes” + “Maybe”) to be contacted by ECRIN to explore a collaboration with the crDSR in order to make secondary use of their clinical study data possible.

7. Next steps

- Complete the Data Sharing Process for the EU-COVAT-1 AGED trial. Remaining actions are the signature of the Data Transfer Agreement, the finalisation of the anonymisation process and the transfer of IPD to the crDSR via an upload to TSD.
- Make the results and conclusions of the survey following up on DSS publicly available. We are still considering whether to opt for a peer-reviewed publication in a scientific journal or an open access report in Zenodo.
- Identify the most interesting use cases among the 18 survey respondents that expressed interest in collaborating with the crDSR to enable data sharing and secondary use. This will happen with the collaboration and support of the EOSC-ENTRUST project⁵⁶ and specific requirements from the clinical research community for the use of TREs (for data transfer, secondary use) will be further refined.
- In terms of sustainability, the work is continued currently within the EOSC-ENTRUST project, while ECRIN and UiO are in constant search of funding opportunities to expand the capabilities of the crDSR and help data providers and reusers enable FAIR clinical research. ECRIN and UiO are willing to ensure minimal in kind support but a more long-term funding route needs to be elaborated.

⁵⁶ <https://eosc-entrust.eu/>

8. Appendix 1: Data Transfer Process – Guideline

PURPOSE

This guideline provides an overview of the steps involved in managing the transfer of material to the clinical research Data Sharing Repository (crDSR). It spans the whole process from initial enquiry, through development and signature of a Data Transfer Agreement (DTA), quality checks on required metadata, the transfer of data objects to the repository, and finally the findability of the available data objects. It describes the responsibilities of the different organisations involved and the information that should be generated as a record of the transfer process.

THIS VERSION

1: 18th July 2024

AUTHORS

Gerd Felder, Christian Ohmann, Mihaela Matei, Steve Canham, Maria Panagiotopoulou, Sergio Contrino, Milen Kouylekov

SCOPE

This guideline applies to all the transfers of data objects to the crDSR.

Terms and Abbreviations

In this document

clinical research Data Sharing Repository	crDSR Or repository	The clinical research Data Sharing Repository (crDSR) is a joint project of the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN) and the University of Oslo (UiO). ECRIN manages the storage of metadata relative to clinical research, so to allow findability and eventual accessibility to clinical research data. UiO operates the secure environment (Trusted Research Environment, TRE) where sensitive data is stored for secondary use. It also enables the secure transfer of the data from the data provider to its TRE called Services for Sensitive Data (TSD).
Trusted Research Environment	TRE	TREs are highly secure computing environments that provide remote access to sensitive data for approved researchers to use in research. Also known as 'Data Safe Haven' or 'Secure Processing Environment'.
Data Object		A Data Object is any file available in electronic form, of any type (document, data, media, etc.). The repository is designed to contain protocols, analysis plans, consent forms, result summaries and other documents associated with a clinical research study, as well as Individual Participant Data (IPD, see dataset definition below).
Dataset		The term Dataset refers to a data object that contains only data – e.g., a spreadsheet, CSV, JSON or XML file, database dump, etc. In the context of the repository, "dataset" will usually refer to the file or files of IPD derived from a clinical trial/study.

Data Object Provider	Provider	A Data Object Provider is an organisation that provides data objects to the crDSR. It must be a legal entity in order to enter into a Data Transfer Agreement with ECRIN. Unless those data objects are already explicitly in the public domain, the Provider is assumed to have the legal power to enter into that agreement, for instance they would hold copyright or intellectual property rights on data objects. For datasets of sensitive personal data, the Provider would be the data controller as defined under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
Data Transfer Agreement	DTA	The Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) is a legal agreement (contract) that governs the transfer of all data objects from the Provider to the crDSR. This agreement will reference the GDPR and associated legislation, and, when applicable, intellectual property law. Each DTA will have an appendix describing the data objects to be transferred to the repository, and – if datasets – whether they are categorised as anonymised or pseudonymised. It will also stipulate any data sharing rules and prerequisites that the Provider wants to impose to Secondary Users.
Repository Manager	RM	The Repository Manager is an ECRIN staff (employee/consultant) who oversees the processes of data transfer and data use and ensures that the secondary use is compliant with the data provider's requirements.

Overview of the process

In broad terms the Data Transfer Process has the following stages:

- I. Initial enquiry and clarification of requirements
- II. Preparation and collection of metadata
- III. Development of Data Transfer Agreement (DTA)
- IV. Agreement of all parties to the DTA
- V. Quality checks on metadata
- VI. Transfer of data objects to the crDSR
- VII. Public release of metadata

Figure 1 provides a diagrammatic representation of these stages, and each is considered in more detail below.

I. Initial enquiry and clarification of requirements

The crDSR landing page contains a “Contact us” button that redirects users to a contact form designed to collect initial enquiries, both of general nature and specific requests to store data. Incoming enquiries are handled by the Repository Manager. ECRIN provides guidance on the requirements of the crDSR, e.g., the need for discovery and descriptive metadata, the need for data to be pseudonymised/anonymised, and the options available for data access. The Data Object Provider will need to indicate the data objects they intend to transfer, and in broad terms the access arrangements they want to see applied to them. The Data Object Provider should also indicate the source study (or studies), and if it is registered also provide a trial registry ID. If the study is not

registered, Data Object Providers will be strongly encouraged to register it before proceeding. The source study, the list of data objects to be transferred, and access arrangements, will be logged in the repository.

II. Preparation and collection of metadata

Metadata for discovery, access and provenance is collected in the repository. The metadata is structured using the ECRIN metadata schema¹, plus some additional fields required to clarify data object management in the repository. Steps include:

- Data Object Providers should nominate one person who will be responsible for the provision of metadata for the study and the associated data objects in the crDSR. Their basic personal details (full name, organisation, role within the organisation, professional e-mail) are communicated to the Repository Manager.
- These individuals are set up by the Repository Manager as named users within the crDSR. User authentication and authorisation is supported by the Life Science Login (a.k.a. Life Science Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure, LS AAI)².
- Data Object Providers should also indicate the person or people who will represent the organisation for the negotiation and signature of the Data Transfer Agreement (DTA). Their basic personal details are stored in the crDSR.
- The Repository Manager initiates a Data Transfer Process and sets up records for the source study or studies. For registered studies, metadata can be automatically extracted from the clinical research Metadata Repository (crMDR)³.
- User permissions are set up so that the person indicated by the Data Object Provider for the submission can edit the study and associated data object information.
- Data objects and the required metadata is then provided by the person indicated by the Data Object Provider for the submission. The crDSR user interface provides guidance to users. In case of doubt, enquiries should be addressed to the Repository Manager.

III. Development of Data Transfer Agreement (DTA)

The repository provides a standard Data Transfer Agreement template, which will be shared with Data Object Providers. The information collected in the crDSR will be used to complete the specific fields in the Data Transfer Agreement with the Data Object Provider. In legal terms, the Data Object Provider remains the data controller, with the crDSR acting as a data processor on behalf of the Data Object Provider.

The DTA will list the data objects and the precise access arrangements to be applied to each, including any embargo periods or any other 'release to public' mechanism. It shall deal with possible revisions of data objects. Individual Participant Data (IPD) shall be qualified, by the Data Object Provider, as either 'pseudonymised' or 'anonymised'. A brief justification of that status shall also be provided. The Data Object Provider shall clarify the legal basis for a) sharing IPD with the crDSR, and b) sharing IPD with others for secondary use (the basis is likely to be the same in both cases).

The Data Object Provider shall also agree to provide the required descriptive metadata file(s) for any IPD, as well as a description of the pseudonymisation/anonymisation steps that were carried out on the IPD.

The crDSR will keep the data securely for 10 years and provide proper backup and other data management services. Possible changes/extensions of the default data storage period can be considered and will be managed through amendments of the initial Data Transfer Agreement. For controlled access objects it will adhere to the Data Object Provider's requested access regime.

Technical and organisational measures to ensure data security are described in the TSD whitepaper and the TSD security handbook, which will be appended to the DTA.

IV. **Agreement of all parties to the DTA**

The DTA should be signed by the legal representative of the Data Object Provider and the legal representative of ECRIN. The signatories and the date are logged in the repository. Introducing non-standard elements during the DTA negotiation is discouraged but can be considered if necessary.

V. **Quality checks on metadata**

The Repository Manager shall check that:

- Any IPD is supported by descriptive metadata.
- Any IPD is supported by a summary description of the pseudonymisation/anonymisation steps taken.

If the checks are successful, the data objects will be transferred to the Trusted Research Environment of TSD (UiO).

VI. **Transfer of data objects to the repository**

The crDSR provides, with its user interface, an easy mechanism for the transfer of data objects. A button for upload is made available when the metadata submission process has been completed and the DTA has been signed. Upload completion is logged in the repository.

VII. **Public release of metadata**

Study and data object metadata are publicly available using the browsing mode of the repository. Data objects that are under controlled access should indicate how access can be requested, again as part of the required metadata.

Figure 1: Stages in the Data Transfer Process.

9. Appendix 2: crDSR Data Sharing Policy

clinical research Data Sharing Repository (crDSR)

- Data Sharing Policy -

PURPOSE

This document is directed to all persons or organisations interested in sharing clinical research data and looking for a secure and non-profit long term storage repository. It describes the policy framework of the clinical research Data Sharing Repository (crDSR) with respect to the management of data objects within it. It first clarifies the interpretation of several key terms, and then sets out the organising principles of the repository's approach. It continues with a high-level description of the options that will be made available for secondary use of data objects (or 'data sharing'), the ways in which Data Transfer Agreements will underpin later data object use, and the data sharing process itself.

This policy document is designed to complement any specific contractual agreement between the crDSR and other organisations, whether for data object transfer or for secondary use. It is also designed to act as a basis for more detailed documents that provide information on how the policy should be interpreted in practice.

THIS VERSION

2.0: 20th August 2024

AUTHORS

Christian Ohmann, Gerd Felder, Mihaela Matei, Steve Canham, Jacques Demotes, Maria Panagiotopoulou, Sergio Contrino

TERMINOLOGY

In this document we refer to the following terms:

1. **clinical research Data Sharing Repository (crDSR)**: The clinical research Data Sharing Repository (crDSR) is a joint project of the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN) and the University of Oslo (UiO). ECRIN manages the storage of metadata relative to clinical research, so to allow findability and eventual accessibility to clinical research data. UiO operates the secure environment (Trusted Research Environment, TRE) where sensitive data is stored for secondary use. It also enables the secure transfer of the data from the data provider to its TRE called Services for Sensitive Data (TSD).

2. **Trusted Research Environment (TRE):** TREs are highly secure computing environments that provide remote access to sensitive data for approved researchers to use in research. Also known as ‘Data Safe Haven’ or ‘Secure Processing Environment’.
3. **Data Object:** A Data Object is any file available in electronic form, of any type (document, data, media, etc.). The repository is designed to contain protocols, analysis plans, consent forms, result summaries and other documents associated with a clinical research study, as well as Individual Participant Data (IPD, see dataset definition below).
4. **Dataset:** The term Dataset refers to a data object that contains only data – e.g., a spreadsheet, CSV, JSON or XML file, database dump, etc. In the context of the repository, “dataset” will usually refer to the file or files of IPD derived from a clinical trial/study.
5. **Data Object Provider** (or ‘**Provider**’ in short): A Data Object Provider is an organisation that provides data objects to the crDSR. It must be a legal entity in order to enter into a Data Transfer Agreement with ECRIN. Unless those data objects are already explicitly in the public domain, the Provider is assumed to have the legal power to enter into that agreement, for instance they would hold copyright or intellectual property rights on data objects. For datasets of sensitive personal data, the Provider would be the data controller as defined under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
6. **Data Transfer Agreement (DTA):** The Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) is a legal agreement (contract) that governs the transfer of all data objects from the Provider to the crDSR. This agreement will reference the GDPR and associated legislation, and, when applicable, intellectual property law. Each DTA will have an appendix describing the data objects to be transferred to the repository, and – if datasets – whether they are categorised as anonymised or pseudonymised. It will also stipulate any data sharing rules and prerequisites that the Provider wants to impose to Secondary Users.
7. **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):** The *Regulation (EU) 2016/679* of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC.
8. **Data Controller:** As defined in the GDPR, the term “data controller” refers to the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data.
9. **Data Use Agreement (DUA)** (also known as Data Access Agreement): The Data Use Agreement (DUA) is a legal agreement (contract) between the Requester (see

below) and ECRIN that governs the secondary use of controlled-access data objects within the crDSR. The DUA will include clauses prohibiting any attempt to re-identify individuals within a dataset, stipulate that datasets should be stored securely and destroyed after use, and require that the Provider and the repository are notified of the results of the secondary use.

10. **Data Object Secondary Users** (or '**Secondary Users**' in short): Data Object Secondary users are individuals (most often researchers) seeking to reuse data objects.
11. **Data Object Requester** (or '**Requester**' in short): The Data Object Requester is the organisation arranging re-use of data objects on behalf of researchers, normally their employer.
12. **Repository Manager**: The Repository Manager is an ECRIN staff (employee/consultant) who oversees the processes of data transfer and data use and ensures that the secondary use is compliant with the data provider's requirements.

A. PRINCIPLES

The following principles form the basis for data sharing within the crDSR:

1. The Data Object Providers retain control over all the data objects they transfer to the repository. In particular, each Provider stipulates the access arrangements to be applied to their objects, identifying those that will be available without restraint, and those that will be under a controlled access regime. For objects under controlled access, the Provider can set fixed prerequisites for access, or reserve the right to review and grant access on a case-by-case basis. For datasets falling under the GDPR or related legislation, the Data Object Provider will remain the Data Controller. For data objects that are explicitly put into the public domain, the Data Object Provider should specify the licence under which such transfer is made.
2. The repository securely stores and processes data objects on behalf of the Data Provider but does not take independent decisions about making data objects that are under controlled access available to Requesters. If, however, the Data Object Provider has stipulated clear criteria for allowing access, the Repository Manager can check a request against those criteria and allow access if the criteria are met, in effect relieving the Data Object Provider of the burden of dealing with such requests.
3. Transfers of all data objects will be the subject of Data Transfer Agreements (DTAs), between the Data Object Provider and ECRIN. The DTA will specify the roles and responsibilities of the organisations involved and state the commitment of the Data Object Provider to submit the necessary metadata and pseudonymisation/anonymisation information for datasets.

4. Controlled access to datasets will be managed using Data Use Agreements (DUAs) to ensure that suitable safeguards are in place. The repository will provide a standard or default Data Use Agreement, though individual Data Object Providers may negotiate amendments to create their specific DUA.
5. The crDSR will hold both anonymised and pseudonymised data, *with the classification being made by the Data Object Provider*. For pseudonymised data the repository will *not* hold any linking or identifying data.
6. To mitigate privacy concerns linked to the secondary use of clinical trial individual level data, the crDSR recommends that the pseudonymised data is further processed after the completion of the clinical trial to ensure removal of any remaining personally identifiable information. Such data processing may involve date re-basing and removal of narrative text fields. This is a recommended yet not mandatory step and the final responsibility for implementing it lies with the Providers. In all cases, the crDSR will require a summary of the privacy-preserving techniques applied.
7. To ensure FAIRness of data objects, all such objects should be linked to metadata on discovery, access and provenance. The Repository Manager will facilitate the adequate provision of metadata, making use of the ECRIN metadata schema for clinical research⁵⁷. Data Object Providers will also be encouraged to ensure originating studies, including observational studies, are registered, which will make the provision of required metadata much easier.
8. Datasets should be associated with detailed descriptive metadata, describing the individual data points. Ideally this would be in a standardised format (e.g., CDISC Define XML) but may be a simple spreadsheet based ‘data dictionary’. The repository should reserve the right to insist on descriptive metadata being available – usually as a public data object, even if access to the dataset itself is controlled.

B. OPTIONS FOR SECONDARY USE

The crDSR provides different access options:

1. Public access, freely available data objects

Many data objects, documents in particular, are expected to be made freely available. No special procedures are necessary for these data objects – there should be a link to them from the metadata, and that link should lead to the document. Normally the document should be visible in the browser and downloaded from there.

2. Data objects with controlled access, managed solely by the Data Provider

This may be applicable, for example, if Data Object Providers have and wish to use their own Data Access Committee. For these Data Objects, users wishing access would be told, via the associated metadata, to contact the Data Object Provider directly.

3. Data objects with controlled access, managed by the crDSR

When requested by Data Object Providers, controlled access management can be delegated to the crDSR. In this case, explicit prerequisites need to be stipulated by the Providers, which are listed in the Data Transfer Agreement. Data Object secondary users enter in contact directly with the Repository Manager, who checks if the prerequisites set by the Data Provider have been met (e.g., there is a protocol describing the proposed use of the datasets). Assuming the prerequisites were clear enough for their fulfilment to be unambiguous, the Repository Manager would then grant access to the data object(s), following the signature of a DUA.

Imposition of an embargo period on data objects with controlled access

Data Object Providers will be offered the option of setting an embargo period. This would extend to a fixed date. *The embargo period should not exceed two years from the date the data objects were transferred to the crDSR.*

C. DATA OBJECT TRANSFER

The Data Object Transfer Process, and the associated Agreement(s), are key to both maintaining the quality of the repository's contents and in establishing the data object access regime for each data object transferred. To support this process, in outline:

1. Any initial enquiries need to be met with a clear explanation of the Data Object Transfer procedure, including the need for the provision of metadata.
2. The collection of metadata for each data object (and for the generating study or studies) is a necessary first step in the Data Object transfer process, as it characterises the objects to be transferred.
3. For each object, the access regime to be applied should be clearly indicated. For controlled access regimes, the nature of any prerequisites to be checked by the Repository Manager should be made clear.
4. For datasets with personal data, the data protection status of the datasets (anonymised or pseudonymised) should be made clear by the Data Object Provider.
5. The data object transfer is governed by a Data Transfer Agreement between ECRIN and the Provider, that will cover all data objects (not just the datasets). Even when data objects have been explicitly placed in the public domain the Data Transfer

Agreement should indicate the specific licence that applies to them. The specific access regime and other details described above should be included within supporting appendices to each Data Transfer Agreement.

6. The details of the data transfer process and the access requirements for each data object need to be stored in the repository.

D. SECONDARY USE

The details of the secondary use process will depend on the stipulations of the Data Object Provider, as written within the Data Transfer Agreement. For controlled access where the repository is involved:

1. The Repository Manager will check if the stipulated prerequisites have been fulfilled by the Data Requester / Secondary Users. If previously instructed to do so, it will also pass the request to a Data Access Committee for their recommendation. If the Data Object Provider's requirements are clearly met the Repository Manager can make the requested data objects available to the Secondary Users. If not, the request will have to be relayed to the Data Object Provider for their final decision.
2. The secondary use of the controlled-access datasets is governed by a Data Use Agreement between the Requester and ECRIN. This will, amongst other things, impose restrictions on usage – normally only for the task explicitly described by the Data Object Secondary Users – and on any further dissemination. It will also prohibit any attempts to re-identify trial participants. To save time and effort, the repository will offer only limited flexibility in the wording of the Data Use Agreement.
3. The progress of the secondary use process needs to be stored in the repository. This system is used to direct and record the granting of the necessary rights to access and / or download data objects.
4. The repository will make public the objective of the secondary use of repository data, making it possible for trial participants to be informed of the nature of the secondary research studies using their personal data. Secondary users will be encouraged to report any publication resulting from their re-use of the data objects.

10. Appendix 3: Supplementary information on EU-COVAT-1 AGED

Inclusion criteria

The main inclusion criteria for EU-COVAT-1-AGED trial Part A and Part B are summarised below:

Subject is \geq 75 years old	
Part A: 3rd COVID-19 vaccination	Part B: 4th COVID-19 vaccination
<p>9 \pm 3 months since the 2nd vaccine dose at time of enrolment for the planned 3rd vaccine dose in the trial.</p> <p>The subject was vaccinated with one of the following vaccination regimens (1st + 2nd dose):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BNT162b2 + BNT162b2 • mRNA-1273 + mRNA-1273 • ChAdOx-1-S + ChAdOx-1-S 	<p>The last dose of the previous COVID-19 vaccinations must have been administered at least 1 month prior to study entry.</p> <p>The subject was vaccinated with one of the following vaccination regimens (1st + 2nd + 3rd dose):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BNT162b2 + BNT162b2 + BNT162b2 • BNT162b2 + BNT162b2 + mRNA-1273 • mRNA-1273 + mRNA-1273 + mRNA-1273 • mRNA-1273 + mRNA-1273 + BNT162b2 • ChAdOx-1-S + ChAdOx-1-S + BNT162b2 • ChAdOx-1-S + ChAdOx-1-S + mRNA-1273

Endpoints

The primary outcome measure of the study was the rate of twofold anti-RBD IgG antibody titer increase 14 days after the second booster against wild-type virus. Secondary endpoints included the increase in vaccine-induced antibody titers and changes in neutralising antibody activity against the wild-type virus and variants of concern (VOC) after 14 days. Detailed list given in the table below. In addition, the safety endpoints included unsolicited Adverse Events (AE) until the end of the trial, solicited AEs for 7 days after the fourth dose and rate of Severe Adverse Events up to 3 months after the fourth dose.

In brief, the analysis so far has concluded that a second booster vaccination with either BNT162b2 or mRNA-1273 yielded a substantial antibody titer increase 14 days after vaccination in participants of advanced age. Full-dose mRNA-1273 (100 μ g) provided a higher antibody titer than BNT162b2 (30 μ g), with an overall similar safety profile for participants aged \geq 75 years^{37,38}.

Primary Outcome Measure		
Outcome Measure	Measure Description	Time Frame
Antibody titre increase 14 days after 4 th vaccination dose.	Rate of 2-fold antibody titre increase 14 days after 4th vaccination dose measured by qualitative enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (Anti-RBD-ELISA) against wildtype virus.	14 days after 4th vaccination dose
Secondary Outcome Measures		
Outcome Measure	Measure Description	Time Frame
Antibody titre level against wild-type SARS-CoV-2 after a 4th vaccination dose.	Antibody titre level at 12 months after a 4th vaccination dose measured by a quantitative enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (anti-RBD-ELISA assay).	Up to 12 months after 4th vaccination dose
Neutralizing antibody titre (Virus Neutralisation Assay) after a 4th vaccination dose.	Neutralizing antibody titre (Virus Neutralisation Assay) against wild-type 14 days after a 4th vaccination dose, to be determined in a subgroup only.	14 days after 4th vaccination dose
Neutralizing antibody titre (Virus Neutralisation Assay) after a 4th vaccination dose.	Neutralizing antibody titre (Virus Neutralisation Assay) against variants of Concern (VOC) 14 days after a 4th vaccination dose, to be determined in a subgroup only.	14 days after 4th vaccination dose
Neutralizing antibody titre (Virus Neutralisation Assay) after a 4th vaccination dose.	Neutralizing antibody titre (Virus Neutralisation Assay) against wild-type SARS-CoV-2 at 12 months after a 4th vaccination dose, to be determined in a subgroup only.	Up to 12 months after 4th vaccination dose
Neutralizing antibody titre (Virus Neutralisation Assay) after a 4th vaccination dose.	Neutralizing antibody titre (Virus Neutralisation Assay) against variants of concern at 12 months after a 4th vaccination dose, to be determined in a subgroup only.	Up to 12 months after 4th vaccination dose

11. Appendix 4: Data Transfer Process summary in crDSR

Data Transfer - DTP-0002-EU-VACCELERATE

Transferring Organisation

Universitätsklinikum Köln

Studies

Study ID	Study Title
DSRS-2	Assessing Immune Response of Different COVID-19 Vaccines in Older Adults

Data Objects

Data Object ID	Data Object Title	Access Type	Embargo Until	Data Object Instances
DSRO-5	Advertisement material	Controlled		• PDF
DSRO-6	Trial Protocol	Controlled		• PDF
DSRO-7	Master trial protocol	Controlled		• PDF
DSRO-8	Data Management Plan	Controlled		• PDF
DSRO-9	Biobank Concept	Controlled		• PDF
DSRO-10	Cormimaty Product Information	Controlled		• PDF
DSRO-11	Case Report Form	Controlled		• PDF
DSRO-12	Patient Information and Consent Form	Controlled		• PDF
DSRO-13	Patienteninformation und -Einwilligungserklärung	Controlled		• PDF
DSRO-14	Database Specification	Controlled		• PDF
DSRO-15	Publication Results Part A	Public		• Web text with download
DSRO-16	Publication Results Part B	Public		• Web text with download

Data Objects Controlled Access Prerequisites

None

Associated People

Name	Email
██████████	██████████
██████████	██████████

12. Appendix 5: Survey on DSS

Survey - Follow up on Data Sharing Statement upon clinical study registration

In a recent publication, our group evaluated the informative value of Data Sharing Statements in clinical trial registries (e.g., [ClinicalTrials.gov](https://clinicaltrials.gov)) [1]. For our assessment, a sample of 200 COVID-19 clinical studies was retrieved and the Data Sharing Statements were checked against the intention of sponsors and PIs to make the clinical study dataset available for secondary use (by other research groups, such as meta-analysis networks).

Your study is one of the 131 studies that have been identified as potentially willing to share COVID-19 clinical study data. This survey is conducted to follow up on the results in our recent publication and clarify some data sharing aspects concerning your study.

The survey is provided within the frame of the BY-COVID project (<https://by-covid.org/>) funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme with Grant Agreement No 101046203. The results will be reported in aggregated and anonymous form.

The completion time of the survey is estimated to be 5 minutes.

Your participation would be very valuable!

[1] Ohmann, C., Panagiotopoulou, M., Canham, S. et al. *An assessment of the informative value of data sharing statements in clinical trial registries*. BMC Med Res Methodol 24, 61 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12874-024-02168-8>

* Required

1. Please provide the clinical study registration ID. *

Example: NCT12345678 (see in the invitation e-mail)

2. Please provide the clinical study title. *

Example: Assessment of the Efficacy of Intervention X Amongst Outpatients With COVID-19 (see in the invitation e-mail)

3. What is the current status of the study? *

- Not yet recruiting
- Recruiting
- Active, not recruiting
- Withdrawn / Suspended / Terminated
- Completed

4. In the Data Sharing Statement of your study your willingness to share Individual Participant Data (IPD) is stated. Have you already shared IPD with other researchers outside your institution for further research (e.g., re-analysis, meta-analysis)? *

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

5. Are you still willing to share IPD with other researchers outside your institution for further research (e.g., re-analysis, meta-analysis)? *

- Yes
- No
- Undecided

6. What is the main reason for not sharing IPD with researchers outside the team that generated the data? (max 3 choices) *

Please select at most 3 options.

- Ethical and legal considerations (e.g., uncertainty of the legal basis for sharing and compatibility with the informed consent)
- Lack of time to deposit data (e.g., no personnel available, other institutional priorities)
- Data issues (e.g., organising data in a presentable / re-usable way)
- Credit attribution (e.g., fear of misuse and scooping)
- Other

7. Have you already implemented a data access process for sharing IPD with researchers outside the team that generated the data? *

- Yes, via individual file/data transfer (e.g., email)
- Yes, via an institutional data repository
- Yes, via an external data repository
- No
- None of the above

8. Can you provide a link and/or name the repository that you are using? *

9. What are the specific conditions for making the datasets and associated documentation of your clinical study available to other researchers through a dedicated data repository? *

- If data pseudonymisation/anonymisation services are provided
- If legal and ethical support services are provided
- If the management of data re-use requests can be delegated to the repository
- If appropriate credit attribution is given to our team (as the original data generator) in future publications
- If the services of the data repository are free of charge for me as data provider
- If funding can become available for my research team to do the data submission
- Other

10. ECRIN has built a secure and GDPR-compliant clinical research Data Sharing Repository (crDSR) to facilitate clinical researchers in sharing IPD from clinical studies. Would you be interested in collaborating with such data sharing repository? *

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

11. Share your contact details or those of a member of your team if you wish to be contacted to explore a collaboration with the crDSR and facilitate data sharing and reuse from your clinical research.

Example: John Doe, jon.doe@email.com

12. Any other remark or comment that you would like to share?